

MULTIDIMENSIONAL EVALUATION OF PULMONARY DISORDERS: CLINICAL, BIOCHEMICAL, AND IMAGING PERSPECTIVES

KARIMNAGAR: A CROSS SECTIONAL OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

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Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding: This study did not receive any external funding.

Author Contributions: A.B. and A.G. contributed to study conceptualization and design. A.G. and D.N. performed data collection and clinical evaluation. D.N. Conducted data analysis and interpretation of clinical, biochemical, and imaging findings. D.Na. Prepared the manuscript draft and coordinated manuscript preparation. S.K.D. provided supervision, critical revision, and final approval of the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Received: Mar 27, 2026

Accepted: Apr 24, 2026

Published: Apr 28, 2026

ABSTRACT:

Background: Pulmonary disorders, including infectious and non-infectious diseases, represent a major global health burden contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality. Accurate diagnosis and prognosis require integration of clinical findings with biochemical, haematological, radiological, arterial blood gas, and pulmonary functional assessments.

Objective: To conduct a multidimensional evaluation of pulmonary disorders by analysing clinical presentation along with laboratory, imaging, and functional parameters and determining their association with disease severity and aetiology. Analysed using Chi-square test.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was performed among 251 patients diagnosed with pulmonary diseases. Clinical assessment was supported by laboratory investigations including total leukocyte count, haemoglobin, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, serum albumin, C-reactive protein, lactate dehydrogenase, and adenosine deaminase levels. Radiological evaluation included chest X-ray and computed tomography/high-resolution computed tomography imaging. Pulmonary function testing and arterial blood gas analysis were also

conducted. Participants were categorized into infectious and non-infectious pulmonary disease groups, and statistical correlations were analysed to identify significant associations.

Results: Among 251 participants, 173 (68.9%) had non-infectious pulmonary disorders, whereas 78 (31.1%) had infectious diseases. Pneumonia was the most common infectious condition (20.7%), followed by tuberculosis (8.4%). Anaemia was observed in 34% of patients, and leucocytosis ($>11,000$ cells/mm³) was present in 55%. Elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (>20 mm/hr) was noted in 94% and raised C-reactive protein (>10 mg/L) in 95.6% of in-patients, showing significant association with infectious aetiology ($p = 0.025$). Increased lactate dehydrogenase levels (>222 U/L) demonstrated significant correlation with imaging severity ($p < 0.001$). Abnormal arterial blood gas findings were identified in 56% of patients, with hypoxaemia being the most frequent abnormality.

Conclusion: Multidimensional integrated assessment enhances diagnostic accuracy, disease severity evaluation, and clinical decision-making in pulmonary disorders.

Keywords: *Pulmonary disorders; Multidimensional evaluation; Biomarkers; Imaging assessment; Arterial blood gas; Disease severity; respiratory diseases.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Pulmonary disorders represent a major global public health challenge, contributing significantly to morbidity, mortality, and healthcare burden worldwide. According to the **World Health Organization**, more than 400 million individuals suffer from chronic respiratory diseases such as **asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)**. **Lower respiratory tract infections** remain among the leading causes of death globally, while tuberculosis continues to pose a serious concern in developing countries including India. Non-communicable respiratory diseases such as asthma, COPD, interstitial lung disease, and lung malignancies account for a substantial proportion of respiratory-related fatalities each year.

Accurate diagnosis and management of pulmonary diseases require a comprehensive approach integrating clinical evaluation with biochemical, haematological, radiological, and functional investigations. Biomarkers such as C-reactive protein, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, lactate dehydrogenase, and adenosine deaminase assist in identifying inflammatory activity, disease severity, and underlying aetiology. Imaging modalities including chest radiography and high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) enable early detection of structural abnormalities and disease progression, while pulmonary function testing and arterial blood gas analysis provide functional assessment of respiratory impairment.

Regional data from Telangana indicate a considerable burden of respiratory illnesses with both infectious conditions such as pneumonia and tuberculosis and non-infectious diseases including asthma, COPD, pleural effusion, interstitial lung disease, and lung cancer contributing to hospital admissions and mortality. Despite advances in diagnostic technologies, fragmented evaluation using isolated parameters often delays diagnosis and affects prognosis.

Therefore, a multidimensional evaluation combining clinical findings with laboratory biomarkers, imaging assessment, and functional analysis is essential for accurate disease classification, severity assessment, and therapeutic decision-making. The present study aims to perform a comprehensive multidimensional evaluation of pulmonary disorders and analyse correlations between clinical, biochemical, radiological, and functional parameters among patients attending a tertiary care hospital.

2. Materials and Methods

This prospective, cross-sectional observational study was conducted over a period of six months in the Department of Pulmonary Medicine at Chalmeda Ananda Rao Institute of Medical Sciences. The study site was selected due to the high patient inflow presenting with diverse pulmonary disorders requiring multidisciplinary clinical evaluation, biochemical investigations, and radiological assessment.

A total of 251 participants aged above 18 years diagnosed with suspected or confirmed pulmonary diseases were enrolled using purposive convenience sampling. Patients attending the pulmonary outpatient department as well as those admitted to inpatient wards were included in the study. Individuals presenting with respiratory conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, asthma, pneumonia, tuberculosis, interstitial lung disease, pleural effusion, and lung malignancies were considered eligible. Patients below 18 years of age, those unwilling to provide informed consent, cases with incomplete clinical or diagnostic records, individuals with terminal systemic illness affecting respiratory assessment, and duplicate patient entries were excluded from the study.

Data collection was performed using a structured and validated clinical evaluation proforma designed to record demographic characteristics, clinical history, symptom profile, laboratory findings, imaging reports, and pulmonary functional parameters. All participants underwent detailed clinical assessment followed by biochemical investigations including haemoglobin levels, total leukocyte count, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, serum albumin, C-reactive protein, lactate dehydrogenase, and adenosine deaminase estimation where applicable.

Radiological evaluation included chest X-ray and Computed Tomography/High-Resolution Computed Tomography (CT/HRCT) imaging for identification of structural lung abnormalities. Functional assessment involved pulmonary function testing and arterial blood gas analysis to evaluate respiratory impairment and gas exchange abnormalities.

Patients were categorized into infectious and non-infectious pulmonary disease groups for comparative analysis. Statistical evaluation was performed to determine associations between clinical findings, laboratory parameters, imaging severity, and functional outcomes. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee prior to study initiation, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

3. RESULTS:

TABLE 1: Chief complaints from the study are distributed:

Chief Complaints	n (Sample)	%
Fever	157	19
Shortness of Breath	204	25
Generalized Weakness	33	4
Chest pain	58	7
Wheezing	38	5
Orthopnea	49	6
Cough with sputum	141	17
Cough without sputum	72	9
Cold	36	5
Vomiting	18	2
Oedema	6	1
Total	812	100

Of the 812 complaints that were reported, the most frequent ones were fever (19%) and shortness of breath (25%), suggesting majority of participants showed acute respiratory involvement.

TABLE 2: Distribution of Study Participants According to Respiratory Rate:

Respiratory rate	n(Sample)	%
<20	56	14
20-30	160	22
>30	35	64
Total	251	100

Of the 251 participants, 64% [n = 35] had a respiratory rate greater than 30/min, 22% had a respiratory rate between 20 and 30/min, and 14% had a respiratory rate less than 20/min.

TABLE 3: Distribution of Study Participants According to Oxygen Saturation (SpO₂).

SpO ₂	N (Sample)	%
>95	104	41
95-100	147	59
Total	251	100

Of the 251 individuals, 59% [n = 147] had SpO₂ 95-100%, 41% [n = 104] had SpO₂ <95%, suggesting that the majority had normal oxygen saturation.

Table 4: Relationship between study results and biomarker levels: statistical analysis.

BIOMARKERS VS RADIOLOGICAL FINDINGS

Parameter	Value	df	Significance
PCO ₂ Vs CT/HRCT	32.864	30	0.328
PCO ₂ Vs CHEST X RAY	28.845	27	0.368
PO ₂ Vs CT/HRCT	40.211	30	0.101
PO ₂ Vs CHEST X RAY	22.579	27	0.707
LDH Vs CT/HRCT	76.080	30	<0.001
LDH Vs CHEST X RAY	93.741	27	<0.001
ADA Vs CT/HRCT	67.362	20	<0.001
ADA Vs CHEST X RAY	98.161	18	<0.001
PFT Vs CT/HRCT	56.543	20	<0.001
PFT Vs CHEST X RAY	35.679	18	0.008

The analysis shows that LDH, ADA, and PFT have a highly significant association with both CT/HRCT and chest X-ray findings ($p < 0.001$), indicating a strong correlation with radiological severity. In contrast, PCO₂ and PO₂ did not show a significant association with either imaging modality ($p > 0.05$).

BIOMARKERS VS INFECTIOUS DISEASE

Parameter	Value	d.f	Significance
SpO ₂	2.874	6	0.824
RBC	7.770	6	0.255
WBC	2.303	6	0.890
Serum Albumin	14.497	6	0.025
ESR	1.940	3	0.585
CRP	2.012	6	0.919
PCO ₂	11.594	9	0.237
PO ₂	5.119	9	0.824
AFB	13.761	6	0.032

Sputum Gram Stain	19.862	12	0.070
CT/HRCT	36.891	30	0.180
Chest Xray	76.238	27	<0.001
LDH	18.622	9	0.029
ADA	23.619	6	<0.001
PFT	3.896	6	0.691

There is a statistically significant between the sr. albumin, AFB, sputum gram stain, chest x ray, LDH, ADA levels and infective diagnosis.

BIOMARKERS VS NON-INFECTIOUS

Parameter	Value	df	Significance
SPO2	27.020	16	0.041
RBC	15.238	16	0.507
WBC	17.504	16	0.354
Sr.Albumin	25.795	16	0.057
ESR	5.457	8	0.707
CRP	19.749	16	0.232
PCO2	46.443	24	0.004
PO2	48.248	24	0.002
AFB	52.195	16	<0.001
Sputum gram stain	49.765	32	0.023
CT/HRCT	642.127	80	<0.001
CHEST X-RAY	231.488	72	<0.001
LDH	100.554	24	<0.001
PFT	14.678	16	0.548
ADA	92.501	16	<0.001

In this analysis, SPO2, PCO2, PO2, AFB, Sputum for gram stain, CT/HRCT, Chest X-ray, LDH, and ADA show statistically significant differences [$p < 0.05$] between infectious and non-infectious cases, while RBC, WBC, Serum albumin, ESR, CRP, and PFT are not significant.

DISCUSSION:

- In this cross-sectional observational study of 251 pulmonary disease patients, nearly 47% were above 60 years, indicating increased vulnerability of the elderly to respiratory illnesses, consistent with previous studies by Burney and Bellani. **Male predominance** (57%) was observed, aligning with global respiratory disease trends reported by Lozano and Gupta. **Non-infectious pulmonary diseases** (68.9%) were more common than infectious conditions (31.1%), which matches patterns observed in tertiary

respiratory care studies. Among infectious diseases, pneumonia (20.7%) was the most common, followed by tuberculosis (8.4%), supporting previously reported hospital prevalence trends.

- Hypoxemia ($\text{SpO}_2 < 95\%$) was seen in 40% of patients, while 36.7% had reduced PaO_2 (< 75 mmHg), reflecting impaired oxygenation in pulmonary disorders. A significant correlation between PaO_2 and CT/HRCT severity was observed ($p = 0.046$), indicating that worsening radiological severity is associated with declining oxygenation.
- PaCO_2 levels did not show significant association with disease etiology or radiological severity, suggesting that carbon dioxide retention may not be an early marker in parenchymal lung diseases. These findings emphasize the importance of arterial oxygenation assessment as an indicator of disease severity.
- Leukocytosis (55%), anemia (34%), elevated ESR (94%), and raised CRP (95.6%) were commonly observed, reflecting active inflammation in pulmonary disease. ESR and CRP were elevated in most patients, indicating their usefulness as markers of inflammatory burden, though they lacked specificity for disease etiology.
- Hypoalbuminemia (44.6%) showed significant association with infectious diseases ($p = 0.025$), indicating poor nutritional and inflammatory status. Elevated LDH and ADA levels were significantly associated with radiological abnormalities and infectious etiology, supporting their role as useful biochemical indicators in lung disease evaluation.
- Chest X-ray findings showed strong association with infectious diagnoses ($p < 0.001$), particularly in pneumonia. HRCT abnormalities correlated significantly with pulmonary function impairment, demonstrating the relationship between structural lung damage and functional limitation.
- The integration of clinical findings, biomarkers, ABG analysis, imaging, and pulmonary function tests improved diagnostic and prognostic assessment.
- Overall, the study highlights that a multidimensional diagnostic approach provides better understanding of pulmonary disease severity and supports more effective clinical decision-making.

4. CONCLUSION:

The present study demonstrates the clinical importance of a multidimensional diagnostic approach in the evaluation and management of pulmonary disorders. By integrating biochemical markers, haematological parameters, arterial blood gas analysis, radiological imaging, and pulmonary function assessment, a more accurate characterization of disease aetiology and severity was achieved among patients presenting with diverse respiratory illnesses.

Among the 251 patients evaluated, non-infectious pulmonary diseases constituted the majority, highlighting the increasing burden of chronic respiratory disorders such as asthma, interstitial lung disease, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Infectious conditions, particularly pneumonia and tuberculosis, also contributed significantly to morbidity, emphasizing the continued relevance of early detection strategies. The findings

revealed strong correlations between laboratory abnormalities and imaging severity, supporting the diagnostic and prognostic value of combined clinical and investigative assessment.

Elevated biochemical and haematological markers reflected systemic inflammatory responses and were closely associated with disease progression. Arterial blood gas abnormalities, especially hypoxaemia and hypercapnia, provided important insight into respiratory compromise and functional impairment. Radiological evaluation played a crucial role in differentiating infectious from non-infectious conditions and guided clinical decision-making.

Overall, the study confirms that reliance on isolated diagnostic parameters may lead to incomplete evaluation, whereas an integrated assessment framework significantly enhances diagnostic accuracy, patient stratification, and prognostic prediction. Adoption of a comprehensive multidisciplinary evaluation strategy can facilitate early diagnosis, optimize therapeutic planning, and improve clinical outcomes in patients with pulmonary diseases. These findings support the incorporation of multidimensional assessment protocols into routine pulmonary practice to strengthen evidence-based respiratory care and long-term disease management.

5. Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the support of Vaageswari College of Pharmacy and all participants who contributed to this study.

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